

Educational data mining for predicting academic performance in sub-Saharan African undergraduate stem students: a scoping review

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ABSTRACT

This systematic literature review **examines the effectiveness of educational data mining (EDM)** in predicting the academic performance of undergraduate STEM students in Sub-Saharan African higher education institutions. The study **analyses 41 peer-reviewed articles** to identify key input factors and student involvement factors influencing academic success. The research categorizes these factors into four main themes: previous and current class performance, demographics, socio-economic factors, and e-learning behaviours. A conceptual framework is developed based on student involvement and Input-Environment-Outcomes theories to guide the investigation, highlighting the interplay of student characteristics, educational environment, and academic outcomes. The methodology employs a systematic literature review (SLR) using the PRISMA guideline, with searches conducted across Scopus, Google Scholar, and ProQuest databases. The findings demonstrate that while static data (demographics, prior records) are commonly used, dynamic data (e-learning behaviours) offer a more real-time perspective and understanding of student engagement and predictive accuracy.

Keywords: Educational Data Mining (EDM), Academic Performance Prediction, STEM Students, Sub-Saharan Africa, Systematic Literature Review

1. Introduction

Educational institutions increasingly rely on digital platforms and technologies to conduct teaching and measure student achievement, resulting in large amounts of data related to student activities and the learning process. Educational data mining (EDM) is thus critical in discovering and extracting relevant information from data to assist Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in making educated decisions at all levels. Hence, this data becomes extremely beneficial in monitoring student learning and identifying pupils at risk, as poor academic performance frequently leads to student dropout. Early identification of students at risk can assist the HEIs in providing timely interventions to support these students.

Academic performance in STEM (science, technology, engineering, math) and related fields is of particular concern, as STEM education assists students in solving challenges and exploring new areas crucial for their success in the workforce and in promoting the country's economic growth. However, Science enrolment has historically been low globally, leading to a shortage of STEM skills (Aulck et al., 2017). Student dropouts, specifically in the STEM disciplines, exacerbate this shortage and are recognised as contributing to some sub-Saharan African countries' alarming unemployment rate. While sub-Saharan countries have historically been less active in the STEM fields, improved internet and 5G penetration provide new opportunities in this regard.

This study aims to learn more about the potential of EDM to predict the academic success of undergraduate STEM students, specifically those in Sub-Saharan African countries. To guide the study, the following questions are explored:

RQ1: What key input factors are used in EDM to predict students' academic performance?

RQ2: What are the critical student involvement factors used in EDM to predict students' academic performance?

The next section gives an overview of the related literature. This is followed by a discussion of the methodology employed for the study, that is, the systematic literature review (SLR). Thereafter, the analysis and discussion of the potential predictors of success constructs are dealt with. Finally, implications for practice and concluding remarks are provided.

2. Related Literature

In recent years, there has been an increasing amount of literature on student data. The LMSs used in HEIs generate huge amounts of data associated with students' activities and other peripheral information, which may not be optimised for educational interventions and decision-making (Wanjau & Muketha, 2018). According to Naseem (2021), only one out of the three sub-Saharan African students enrol in STEM courses, while the remaining students opt for non-STEM programs. It is, therefore, imperative that we consider indicators that can assist with mitigating this situation. Cantabella et al. (2019) suggest that using different forms of data to analyse student behaviour may help to identify new relationships. In the following sections, we will consider key factors that play a part in student learning and academic performance.

2.1 Student input factors

Students bring their prior academic experience, demographic, and socioeconomic contexts with them as they enter and navigate the HE system. It is safe to say that these factors affect students' learning. HEIs can assist students in achieving better academic performance through appropriate, targeted intervention programs, if they have access to the necessary data (Zollanvari et al., 2017).

Using the academic results obtained by students in the past to predict future outcomes and discover patterns or relationships in large sets of institutional data is perhaps the most obvious variable used in EDM. Many would assume that students who previously achieved low results are more likely to attain low marks in the future, but this is not always true (Nguyen et al., 2021). EDM provides the opportunity to simultaneously consider past academic results and other variables that may have influenced the performance, giving rise to more accurate predictions (Saa et al., 2019b). For example, Patil et al. (2017) used students' previous semester performance to predict their Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA).

Similarly, student demographic and socio-economic factors are among the most common factors mentioned in the EDM literature. Alom and Courtney (2018) found that gender plays a critical role in success rates, specifically in certain Australian states, while Alturki et al. (2022) indicate that there is no clear indication of the extent to which gender as an independent factor plays a role in predicting academic performance. Taodzera et al. (2017) showed that the school location and ethnicity played an important role in predicting student success in engineering at a

South African university. Socio-economic factors, such as parents' education, occupation, and family income, have also been shown to be significant predictors of student success (Bussu et al. (2019). Supporting this view, bin Roslan and Chen (2022) writes that family attributes are an essential determinant of students' academic performance. In particular, Alyahyan and Düşteğör (2020) uncovered a positive correlation between students' demographics and their academic performances.

Once students enter HEIs, their academic behaviour – beyond just their performance – may provide useful predictive insights. Several studies (for example, Al-Shabandar et al., 2017 and Hussain et al., 2018), have found that student academic success correlates with student click-stream LMS behaviours and their demographics. Similarly, Zacharis (2015) showed that the frequency of solving quizzes, viewing files, and reading and posting messages was a significant predictor of student success. Interestingly, in an earlier study (Sorour et al., 2014, p. 1) it emerged that the students' LMS comments after lessons predicted student success with an accuracy of 82.6%. According to Khan et al. (2021), students' attendance and engagement levels are useful in predicting students' likelihood of dropping out or in identifying the characteristics of high-performing students. Helal et al. (2018) argues that different sets of attributes play a major role in predicting academic performance in different student sub-populations.

2.2 Student Involvement Theory

Student involvement theory considers student participation, resources, and individual abilities as impacting the student's academic progress (Austin, 1984, as cited in Lei et al., 2017). The effectiveness of educational courses or programs in encouraging student involvement has the potential to improve student development and success (Lei et al., 2017). Jaafar et al. (2012) maintain that various types of student involvement influence students' development, namely: student governance, athletic involvement, academic involvement, and student-faculty interaction. Consequently, the quantity and quality of physical and psychological energy students invest in educational experiences vary from student to student. It is incumbent upon leadership and policymakers in HEIs to focus on these involvement factors to improve retention and other outcomes (Kim, 2017).

2.3 Student outcomes

While students' positive progression through HE is the desired educational outcome, all too frequently, it is difficult to retain students in the system, as they drop out.

Lack of educational funding is one of the factors that lead to dropping out. For students to obtain desirable outcomes, they must choose suitable courses (Nguyen et al., 2021) that align with their interest and competence. Various factors, such as interest, demands, and competence, influence students' decisions on course enrollment. Systems that provide recommendations on the appropriate program choices for students by using their assessed grades have resulted in studies focusing on developing EDM course recommendation systems. Chang et al.'s (2016) study used collaborative filtering to recommend suitable study programs. Another key factor is the failure of HEIs to prepare young adults for relevant professions, triggering massive economic development losses as fewer professionals suitable for the 4IR are produced by HEIs (Sani et al., 2020). Now this phenomenon has escalated with the emerging generative AI technologies.

However, predicting students' academic performance is a multifaceted and complex process (Ndou et al., 2020b). Hence, we develop a conceptual framework to provide a clear theoretical framing for the study, including those constructs identified as important in the introductory literature.

3. Conceptual Framework

This study develops a conceptual framework for HE data mining based on relevant variables from the literature to understand EDM's effectiveness in forecasting students' academic performance. The conceptual framework relies on the student involvement theory and the Input-Environment-Outcomes theory as its foundation.

Astin and Antonio (2012) states that from the HEIs' perspective, the delivery of a course or program that includes three attributes: student inputs, educational environment, and outcomes, is considered a model. The inputs refer to the personal characteristics that a student initially brings to a program or course, such as race, gender, level of competency at entry, educational experiences, family background, and personal expectations of future courses (Bard, 2016). The student inputs may also involve previous academic grades (Saa et al., (2019a). The environment attribute comprises students' actual experiences during a program (Lei et al., 2017), focusing on students' development activities in an educational environment. The student development environment includes the LMS and student information system (SIS) of the HEI. The third attribute, outcomes, includes school retention, career orientation, incremental knowledge, and graduation throughput. Additionally, the outcomes embrace the resulting students' attitudes, beliefs, values, and knowledge after completing a program. In other words, outcomes refer to the abilities that HEIs attempt to develop throughout the current course or program (Chigbu & Nekhwevha, 2021). Hence, outcomes can be defined by time, outcome, and outcome type, influenced by both the educational environment and the inputs. Inputs inform students' attitudes and choices in their educational environment and significantly shape their academic outcomes (Patton et al., 2019).

The Higher Educational Data Mining (HEDM) conceptual framework developed in this study includes three major attributes: inputs, student development environment, and outcomes, as shown in Figure 1. Students' inputs influence the students' involvement and hence the student development environment (relationship A).

Figure 1: EDM Decision-Making Framework

The student development environment is where the student interacts with teachers. It contains two significant parts, which are EDM (includes pre-processing, EDM tools, and techniques) and decision-making. The data obtained from educational settings can be in structured and unstructured data formats, with unstructured formats being more complex to process. Thus, data from the student involvement environment must be pre-processed or cleaned before it is used for EDM analyses (Lei et al., 2017). The resulting information then needs to be interpreted for effective decision-making.

Relationship B, the result of the HE decision-making in the students’ development environment, impacts the student outcomes and forms a feedback loop to the student inputs as input to the next learning cycle. In other words, while input and involvement data are considered independent variables in this framework, they are indirectly influenced by educational decisions made in the student development environment or HEI (Astin & Antonia, 2012). Relationship C indicates the direct impact of the students’ inputs on their outcomes. Student outcomes are a dependent variable influenced by input and involvement data and decision-making. Outcomes data are the result of the impact of decision-making and are used to evaluate the quality of the student development environment (Lei et al., 2017). The outcomes variable reflects the quality or effectiveness of decision-making, as shown by relationship B. The outcomes from decision-making consist of academic performance, decision support, dropout and retention rates, and recommendations. Academic performance measures the ability of a student to graduate from current or future courses (Meghji et al., 2018). Thus, EDM uses students’ historical and current

academic performance data to provide recommendations for the phases following their courses. Recommendations on appropriate programs through the assessed student grades will assist them in choosing more suitable courses throughout their program (Nguyen et al., 2021). Therefore, decision support driven by knowledge is useful for educational stakeholders in making more reasonable and appropriate decisions (Mgala & Mbogho, 2015). The aim is to improve performance, increase retention, reduce attrition, and increase the throughput rates (Adejo & Connolly, 2017).

The next section describes the methodology followed to obtain the studies for review and to answer the research questions.

4. Methodology

This study is part of a larger study that used a systematic literature review (SLR) methodology to examine EDM's effectiveness in predicting sub-Saharan African STEM students' academic performance. SLR was employed to review articles using explicit and systematic methods for transparency and to minimise bias, so that the study can be reproduced, providing reliable findings (Saa et al., 2019b). The most commonly used reporting guideline for SLRs, the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) (Rethlefsen et al., 2021) was used.

4.1 Choice of Database

The search strategy for the study involved three commonly used databases to which the authors had free academic access: Scopus (<https://www-scopus-com.ukzn.idm.oclc.org/>), Google Scholar (<https://scholar.google.co.za/>), and ProQuest (<https://www.proquest.com/>). These databases are widely used in EDM reviews and involve studies investigating the predictive modelling of STEM student performance (Namoun & Alshantqi, 2021).

4.2 Search Strategy

Specific keywords and concepts related to educational data mining were used together with the wildcard symbol (*) to accommodate different spellings and Boolean operators, such as AND, OR, to configure the search to find more precise and relevant results. The final search string used was: "Effectiveness" AND ("data mining" OR "educational data mining" OR "learning analytics") AND ("classification" OR "clustering") AND ("predicting student academic performance") AND ("science" OR "technology" OR "engineering" OR "math*") AND ("course*" OR "program*") AND ("undergraduate" OR "university") AND ("Africa*" OR "Sub-Saharan Africa*" OR "developing countr*")

This research considered empirical research studies for inclusion published in the five years, from 2017 to 2021, as any study before 2017 might have outdated information due to rapid changes in EDM (Chanthiran et al., 2022). The inclusion and exclusion criteria for studies to be considered for review and analysis are provided in Table 1.

4.3. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Table 1: Eligibility Criteria

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Must be classified as STEM or a related discipline EDM research	Systematic reviews
Must be published between 2017 and 2021	Primary or secondary education
Must be conducted in higher educational institutions in Sub-Saharan Africa	Conducted in countries outside of sub-Saharan Africa
It should be written in English	Not available in full text

4.4 Quality Assessment Criteria

A quality assessment checklist of six criteria was used to evaluate the studies’ quality for inclusion in the final review. The checklist was adapted from Kitchenham et al. (2009), shown in Table 2. Every study was scored for each criterion question using a three-point scale, “yes” equals 1 point, “partially” equals 0.5 points, and “no” equals 0 points. Studies that scored 3 points and above passed the assessment and were used in further review (Table A1).

Table 2: Quality Assessment

	Question
Q1.	Is the study focusing on sub-Saharan African undergraduate students in STEM fields?
Q2.	Is the data collection adequately explained in detail?
Q3.	Is the reliability of the study explained?
Q4.	Does the study interpret the results of the predictive analysis?
Q5.	Are the conclusions adding to the literature?
Q6.	Is the study expanding your understanding of EDM?

Figure 2 illustrates the process followed to obtain the relevant set of studies that met the eligibility conditions described above.

Figure 2: PRISMA flowchart

An initial search returned 521 articles from Google Scholar, 19 articles from ProQuest, and 0 Scopus articles. The search string was then refined, and Google Scholar generated 2070 results sorted by relevance, with only the first 1000 relevant results returned by default. ProQuest yielded 1283 records. This provided a total of 2823 articles for screening (i.e., 521+19+2283). During screening, 21 duplicate articles were removed, and 2734 were identified as not relevant. The remaining 68 studies were reviewed for eligibility, with 27 additional studies being excluded, because they represented a review or SLR study (1), were not in HE (3), were not based in sub-Saharan Africa (3), were not EDM research (19), and were not available in full text (1). The final sample for analysis comprised 41 studies, named and referred to as [S1], [S2], etc. Table A.1 (in Appendix A) contains the complete set of studies. Finally, the selected studies were assessed for quality according to the quality assessment criteria outlined above. All 41 studies attained a score equal to or above 3 (50%). The top-scoring studies are [S30], [S33], [S35], and [S36], with scores equal to 6 (100%) (see Table A.2 in Appendix A). Two types of analyses were performed: bibliometric and thematic analyses. According to Guzmán-Valenzuela et al. (2021), bibliometric analyses provide descriptive statistics that reveal a particular topic’s publication trends.

5. Results

The analysis is organized into two sections. The first section consists of the bibliometric analysis and provides descriptive statistics relating to the common trends in the reviewed studies, followed by the thematic analysis of the findings.

5.1 Bibliometric results

Selected studies based on year of study, country of study, and publication type are shown in Figures 3-5

Figure 3: Distribution by year

Figure 4: Distribution by country

Figure 5: Distribution by publication type

There was an increasing trend in publications from 2017 to 2019, and then a decrease in 2020, likely due to COVID-19; and in 2021, there was a rise again to 10 studies (24% of the sample). Figure 4 shows the distribution of studies by country, with South Africa (56%) and Nigeria (27%) dominating in the sub-Saharan African context. From this SLR, a broad spectrum of publication types emerged (as shown in Figure 5), most of which came from journal articles (56%), followed by thesis papers (31.7%), 9.7% and 2.4% of conference papers and book sections, respectively. This set of papers allowed us to gain a broad perspective of the research problem, i.e., students’ academic performance prediction.

5.2 Thematic Analysis – Academic Performance Analysis

A thematic analysis of existing literature is presented in this section, which attempts to identify significant factors influencing students’ academic performance prediction and the effectiveness of EDM. Student academic performance analysis and prediction are EDM’s two commonly investigated research areas. Even though their goals vary, the effects of performance analysis considerably influence performance prediction. This thematic analysis presents studies highlighting the important factors in the predictions. The thematic analysis is represented in a structured format, indicating the main theme, sub-themes, and items in Table 3 for ease of reading.

Table 3: Academic Performance Analysis: Sub-Themes and their Items of Interest

Sub-Themes	Individual Items	Studies	Frequency
Previous Grades and Current Class Performance	<p><i>Pre-enrolment Grades</i> Matric results, Admission Point Score (APS), National Benchmark Tests (NBT), Outcome, Admission Matriculation Board (JAMB) score, Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination (UTME) score, Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE) score, student’s grade point average (GPA) at secondary school, placement test score on entry to university,</p> <p><i>Internal assessment</i> Current GPA for courses taken, raw scores, Group assignment marks, Tutorial</p>	[S1], [S2], [S3], [S4], [S5], [S6], [S7], [S8], [S9], [S10], [S11], [S12], [S14], [S15], [S16], [S17], [S18], [S19], [S20], [S21], [S22], [S23], [S24], [S25], [S26], [S27], [S28], [S29], [S30], [S31], [S32], [S33], [S34], [S35], [S36], [S37], [S38], [S39], [S40], [S41]	40

	<p>marks, Test marks, Bonus marks, Individual assignment marks,</p> <p><i>External assessment</i></p> <p>First to third-year GPA, Final CGPA, grades obtained in the prerequisite module, , , Class average, Cumulative weighted Average (CWA), cumulative grade point average (CGPA)</p>		
Demographics	<p><i>Personal demographics</i></p> <p>Age, gender, race, Marital status Home language, Additional language, Disability indicator, Employment status Place of birth</p> <p><i>Academic demographic data</i></p> <p>Student’s major, current year of study, year of admission, number of modules registered, bursary, Full-time or part-time study, Number of years in degree, Year of graduation, Field of study, Credits obtained, Years in the system, Level of study, Persistence (a count of modules attempted), Number of modules completed, Number of modules passed the first time, Student status (attrition or graduated), Progression outcome type</p> <p><i>Other demographics</i></p> <p>Number of employed parents or guardians, High school quintile ranking, Admission date, Email address, Telephone number, Home address, Name of previous School, Country of origin, Geopolitical zone, Nationality, Financial sources, financial aid indicator,</p>	[S1], [S2], [S3], [S4], [S5], [S6], [S7], [S8], [S9], [S10], [S11], [S12], [S13], [S14], [S16], [S17], [S20], [S21], [S22], [S23], [S24], [S25], [S26], [S27], [S28], [S29], [S30], [S32], [S33], [S34], [S35], [S36], [S37], [S38], [S39], [S40], [S41]	37
Socio-economic data	<p><i>Environment and Family Characteristics</i></p> <p>Residence, School quintile, Rural/Urban School, Class communication, Proper guidance, Study habit, Student Attitude, Teaching Aids, Family Stress, Parent education, Family size, Family income, Family support structure, Motivation, Academic self-efficacy, Stress and time pressure, Parents survey answers, parent sponsor, Parent school satisfaction, Study hours, Class attendance, course or program, Event context, Event name, Origin, IP address,</p>	[S5], [S7], [S8], [S9], [S11], [S14], [S15], [S17], [S22], [S25], [S27], [S29], [S31], [S34], [S36], [S37], [S41]	24
E-learning Activities	<p><i>Engagement with LMS data</i></p> <p>Discussion, Time of discussion, viewing announcements, Students' virtual learning environment (VLE), Description, Components, Time spent in LMS activity, uploaded assignment, affected user, Event name, Event context, raised hands, LMS Visual resources</p>	[S9], [S12], [S14], [S30], [S34], [35]	6

Choosing the correct predictors is crucial in achieving an accurate prediction. Therefore, factors influencing the process of knowledge discovery must be identified before the process of predicting students’ academic performance (Helal et al., 2018). Moreover, the increase in student dropouts and the decrease in their success are the main concerns of many HEIs. Hence, a preliminary analysis of student performance can assist HEIs in this instance (Khan & Ghosh, 2021).

According to Zollanvari et al. (2017), identifying input factors as predictors for subsequent use in predicting students' academic performance is difficult, as several factors influence academic performance in non-linear ways. The most common items explored include previous and current class performance, demographics, socio-economic factors, and e-learning behaviours. The findings of this section are summarized in Table 4.

5.2.1. Previous and current class performance

The previous and current class performance theme is the most frequently occurring theme in this analysis, as it was cited across 40 of the 41 studies reviewed. The previous and current class performance factors include pre-enrolment grades and internal and external assessments.

Pre-enrolment Grades: These factors relate to students' scores or grades before enrolment, including grades earned in prerequisite courses, matric scores, and admission point scores (APS). Regarding using previous grades for students' academic performance prediction, the commonly used features are matric and APS scores ([S1], [S15], [S21], [S32], [S36], [S40]). Although matric results have been essential in predicting students' academic performance, some studies do not regard them as necessary ([S25], [S27]).

[S1] used two datasets to develop a recommendation system to guide students on their academic path, one containing the undergraduate science course registration data and another containing the corresponding matric results. The results show that EDM classification models were highly accurate in predicting whether a new student was likely to graduate in 3 years, more than three years, or fail to meet the requirements using their matric results and enrolment data. [S15] developed a predictive model using attributes including first-semester university results, average matriculation, lecturer competency, self-study hours, and attendance to show that these attributes can predict a first-year university student's academic performance before their final exams.

[S21] used students' APS scores and lecturer data for students' academic performance prediction. The findings suggested the possibility of predicting students who will succeed in an engineering course of their choice.

In contrast, [S25] predicted undergraduate students' likelihood to drop out using the students' schooling, biographical, and individual characteristics. These factors were found to be significant. However, they rejected using only pre-university factors such as the National Benchmark Test (NBT) and matric results as a primary schooling system measure for predicting students' academic performance. They suggested that these pre-university factors should be used in university performances, especially first-year performances.

The findings showed that high school grades and previous computer knowledge were not significant in predicting students' academic performance.

According to [S32], using discrete-time models also enabled testing the influence of Mathematics and APS scores on students' dropout risk. It was assumed that the dropout risk was more prominent in the first year of study and diminished over time. The findings revealed that the effects were insignificant and remained constant over time.

[S36] aimed to discover factors influencing first-year engineering students' academic performance. The significant factors were ethnicity, school province, age, and mathematics and physics grades.

[S40] developed a general EDM framework using ensemble methods for predicting STEM students' academic performance. Five significant factors significantly influenced the choice of students enrolling in STEM programs.

These factors included the high school final exam score, beliefs in competency for succeeding in a STEM-related career, inspiration from the high school teachers, and expected career flexibility.

Internal Assessment Grades: Internal assessments in the literature are related to the internally evaluated grades in class tests, quizzes, assignments, or other related elements. Most literature focusing on this aspect positively influenced final performance ([S2], [S14], [S23]). The results also indicated a significant influence of class attendance ([S13]) and group assignment scores ([S23]) on students' academic performance prediction. [S2] used predictors such as individual grades, year of completion, year of admission, grades achieved from the courses enrolled, and the degree class to predict the final grades of Communication and Information Technology students. This study found that timely completion of the first two courses leads to a high grade in computer architecture programs. The grades in the discrete mathematics and programming course significantly influence students' academic performance prediction.

The findings from study [14] revealed that the final mark, assignment mark, tutorial mark, test mark, bonus mark, including some external assessment grades like National Benchmark Test (NBT) math mark, math prerequisites, and math high school mark, significantly predicted students' academic performance. [S23] used EDM to predict students' success and suggested that performance in a specific type of assessment may serve as an indicator of student performance. The results showed that group assignments positively correlated with the pass rate. Hence, students must be encouraged to participate more actively in group assignments, as this may not only result in a positive outcome in the specific task but may also point to a positive benefit of such engagement, impacting overall performance.

However, to explore the situation of students feeling challenged [S38] implemented five EDM models to identify at-risk Business Statistics students sufficiently early to provide strategic interventions to improve performance. The significant factors that could identify at-risk students were marks achieved in average quiz marks, semester test one marks, and a prerequisite course as well.

External Assessment Grades: EDM researchers frequently explore Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA) as a form of external assessment for predicting student performance. Notably, CGPA focuses on all previous performances of students in their program or degree and combines them into a single value. Hence, most of the literature establishes CGPA as an important factor in students' academic performance prediction ([S3], [S11], [S17], [S37], [S39], [S41]). However, some studies have also argued that CGPA is ineffective when used alone in students' academic performance prediction ([S7], [S32]). A study by [S3] used the first three years' GPA of students to predict the final year CGPA. This study found that the first-year GPA had a significant influence on engineering students' academic performance. In contrast, [S7] found a weak correlation between students' best six GPAs and CGPA.

[S11] predicted students' academic performance only for students with a CGPA of less than 3.0 and categorised them into high and low risk. In this study [11], it was found that the average of the pre-enrolment grades (Senior Secondary Certificate of Education (SSCE) score, post-unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination (UTME) score, Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board (JAMB) score) also played a significant role in predicting students' CGPA. Moreover, other demographic data like secondary school type, weekly study time, sponsor type, sponsor support, sponsor income, sponsor qualification, secondary school area, years before admission, work and study, university accommodation, postgraduate degree, course interest, and sports activeness were significant factors for.

[S17] used EDM to analyse students' performance, including their CGPA and grade class. The results revealed that out of the 21 first-year courses offered, only seven courses, such as mathematics, physics, and chemistry, commonly occur together as failed courses (related STEM), and they significantly influence students' academic performance prediction. Another study by [S32] found that CGPA predicts a reduced graduation potential than what occurs when the impact of single GPAs on graduation potential is modelled alone.

[S37] used predictors such as preparatory school GPA, entrance examination results, and first-semester first-year academic performance to predict the CGPA achieved by students. The results showed that these factors significantly influenced students' academic performance prediction.

[S39] predicted students' academic performance using a dataset with attributes such as level of matric achieved, gender, program, first semester GPA, second semester GPA, CGPA, and current standing. These factors proved significant in predicting students' academic performance.

[S41] predicted the students' academic performance using CGPA, in addition to pre-enrolment grades and demographic data such as high school exam scores, region, gender, and age, to enable efficient and timely implementation of interventions. This study found that students with high JAMB grades are more likely to attain a high CGPA. Additionally, this study found that students in their third and fourth years were more likely to attain a high CGPA.

From the above data, academic performance factors such as pre-enrolment, internal assessment, and external assessment grades are essential factors that should be considered in any EDM project. The evidence also suggested that future work should focus on students' academic performance prediction using pre-enrolment and enrolment data using EDM early, such as the first year of a course, to assist HEIs in making timely and meaningful decisions to support low-performing students.

5.2.2 Demographic Data

Exploring students' academic and demographic factors is common in students' academic performance analysis. The most frequent demographic characteristics in the analysis were age and gender. Other demographic factors, such as ethnicity and race, were used as predictors and were found to be significant when paired with other demographic features.

Personal demographic data: Age - The commonly used demographic factor to predict academic performance is age. Many studies have shown a strong correlation between age and performance ([S1], [S5], [S16], [S25], [S29], [S33], [S36]), suggesting that older students are more experienced, highly motivated, and possess effective study practices. However, one study found that age does not significantly influence students' academic performance prediction ([S41]), and out of 24 studies that used age to predict students' academic performance, only eight studies reported its significance in predicting students' academic performance.

Gender - The second most used demographic factor in students' academic performance prediction is gender. This is not surprising given the extensive debate in EDM literature about the relationship between students' gender and academic performance (Alturki et al., 2022).

Of the nineteen studies identified that used gender to predict students' academic performance, only two of them ([S26], [S32]) showed students' gender as not significant. In other studies ([S5], [S25], [S34], [S41]), it was found that either the males or the females performed better in predictions. [S4] examined students' ethnic influence on the EDM models' predictive accuracy. The findings revealed that students' ethnicity was not significant in

predicting their performance. Hence, using ethnicity alone to predict students' academic performance is inadequate.

Academic Demographic data: [S20] showed that the number of deferments of students highly determined the progression rate of students. More students were deferring than those dropping out of their courses altogether. [25] indicated that, in addition to other factors, the number of years in a degree and having a Mathematics major influenced the academic prediction.

Other Demographic Features: The other demographics available in the literature include school quintile, province of the student, country, home language, deferment rate, employment status, financial sources, race, and ethnicity, which have often been used as predictors. These factors have been widely explored in literature and found to influence students' academic performance prediction significantly ([S1], [S8], [S16], [S25], [S32]). However, in studies [S4] and [S11], it was found that in predicting students' academic performance, ethnicity and marital status, respectively, are not significant. It was also found that urban students performed better than rural students ([S41]).

[S23] results showed that bursary and group assignments positively correlated with the pass rate. [S25] found that the most contributing factors were biographical and individual characteristics such as race, home language, home country, and home province, which played an essential role in predicting students' academic performance.

Interestingly, [S32] found that English first-language students were more at-risk of dropping out than those who used it as a second language, as language is often considered a limiting factor in student success, which contradicts what is commonly found in the literature. Another factor identified by [S41] is that students from urban areas were more likely to attain a high CGPA.

5.2.3 Socio-economic Factors

The socio-economic factors related to the learning environment and family data.

- **Environment and Family data:** Some studies have shown a positive relationship between socio-economic status and academic success ([S11], [S16], [S32]). Family data such as income, parent occupation, and financial support affect students' academic performance, specifically students' dropout behaviours ([S10], [S16], [S26], [S29]). In some studies, place of residence was highly influential and notable in influencing student dropout behaviour ([S32]). Also, living locations, annual family income, family sizes, family status, parents' occupations, gender, and other pre-enrolment factors were found to be crucial in predicting students' academic performance [S26].

[S16] found that poor social integration, the field of placement, mismatched areas of interest, poor commitment, and poor preparation are significant factors leading to students dropping out.

[S32] used EDM methods to predict the timing and occurrence of student dropout in undergraduate engineering courses. The study found that the outcomes of the type of residence differ with time. For example, first-year students in private accommodations were more likely to drop out than on-campus students. In contrast, third-year students living in private-based accommodations were less likely to drop out than on-campus students.

5.2.4 E-Learning Behaviours

E-Learning behaviour refers to students' online interaction with learning management systems (LMSs). In this study we refer to e-learning behaviour as engagement with LMS data.

Engagement with LMS data: The commonly extracted data from LMSs include students' e-learning activities such as solving quizzes, viewing files, submitting content, and reading and posting messages, which are significant predictors of students' academic performance ([S34]). Other predictors include opening resources and responding to course evaluation surveys ([S9], [S12]). Engagement with LMS data obtained from LMS is one of the primary metrics identified for measuring students' academic performance ([S35]). For example, study [S30] revealed a strong relationship between student activity logs obtained from Moodle LMS and students' academic performance. Specifically, [S9] showed that visiting resources, announcement views, raised hands, parents answering a survey, discussions, and parent-school satisfaction were significant in students' academic performance predictions. Interestingly, [S12] used a clustering technique with data from an LMS to group the low-performing students into two groups for knowledge discovery. Their results revealed that low-level absentee students whose parents do not participate enough in their studies are more likely to perform poorly than those whose parents participate. A study by [S14] identified academic factors, such as engagement variables and course assessments, at specific intervals in a semester, providing helpful recommendations linked to those intervals. Together with students' pre-enrolment grades, internal assessments, and external assessments like prior academic information and high school grades, they were able to predict students' academic performance.

Similarly, [S34] examined features from an LMS system, such as personality, behaviour, and background, to predict students' academic performance using EDM methods. These e-learning behavioural factors include uploaded assignments, time spent working on courses, and participation in online group discussions. The findings showed that students' e-learning behaviours and personalities significantly influenced their academic performance more than their background.

Further analysis showed that study [S35] developed ensemble EDM models for early and accurate prediction of at-risk students' performance using students' weekly Virtual Learning Environment (VLE) and demographic data, indicating significant influence on students' academic performance.

5.3. Source of Data for Academic Performance Analysis

Data Sources: Three data sources were identified in the 41 studies examined: Moodle learning management system (LMS) logs, student information system (SIS), and a survey. Figure 6 shows that most studies (35) employed data records and sources available through SIS that contained student information such as enrolment, background, and admissions data. Moodle LMS activity logs were the least used data collection method, as cited in six studies (15%). Finally, the survey method was the second most utilised data-gathering method, appearing in four studies (10%). Since some studies used more than one data collection source, the total percentage of the data collection techniques is not equal to 100%.

Figure 6: Distribution by data collection source

However, the socio-economic details of students may not be readily available. In such cases, researchers can acquire these details from students through surveys. EDM researchers can also extract instructor attributes and prior knowledge data from the survey.

Predicting students' academic performance using external assessment data, specifically grades from the program's first two years, yielded higher performance than those that included only pre-university or demographics data.

Year Level and Course Level: In this analysis, a few studies focused on predicting students' academic performance at the year level. Studies that use the year level perform less in predicting students' academic performance than those studies at both the degree level and course level. For example, [S2] showed that a high GPA in discrete mathematics, programming, network, and computer architecture courses significantly predicts students' final grades. Predicting students' academic performance at the course level is the second most cited theme. The effectiveness of predicting whether students might pass or fail a course is helpful because it can assist HEIs in making early, efficient, and timely decisions and thereby improve the academic performance of students ([S14]).

[S6] developed EDM algorithms for predicting students' competence in computer programming. The findings indicated that the factors significantly influencing students' academic performance in programming were self-efficacy, previous knowledge of programming, lecturer's performance, motivation, and interest level. However, in [13], the findings indicated that the determining factors of programming students' performance were "fearful perceptions" of programming courses, the attitude of students and lecturers, student health, student attendance, university facilities, and erratic power supply. Course-level predictions were specific to the course characteristics. What is interesting is that it confirms what might seem like a straightforward assumption. While one might expect that incorporating grades from the early years of a program would improve predictive accuracy, having empirical evidence supporting this expectation is crucial. The significance of this result is in its validation of the common-sense notion, emphasizing that, within the context of sub-Saharan STEM education, using early academic indicators is not only intuitive but also empirically proven to significantly enhance the effectiveness of EDM in predicting students' academic performance. This reinforces the idea that program-specific factors, like early academic achievements, can play a more pivotal role in predictive modelling than what might be initially assumed or expected. It highlights the importance of data-driven insights in shaping our understanding of the factors influencing academic outcomes.

6. Discussion

The aim of this study was to determine the effectiveness of EDM in predicting sub-Saharan African undergraduate STEM students' academic performance. By analysing 41 selected studies that focused on predicting students' academic performance in sub-Saharan African HEIs, we addressed the research questions.

RQ1 What key input factors are used in EDM to predict sub-Saharan African undergraduate STEM students' academic performance?

All 41 studies showed that one of the most crucial factors influencing students' academic performance is previous and current class performance. The external assessment (such as tests, examinations, or evaluations conducted externally), internal assessment (such as assignments, quizzes, projects, or any form of assessment designed by the course instructor), and pre-enrolment grades (performance records of students before entering the specific STEM program) were used in all the selected literature that predicted students' academic performance. These factors collectively form a robust set of indicators, combining standardized measures, ongoing classroom evaluations, and historical academic records to provide a comprehensive insight into students' potential academic outcomes. This finding aligns with the investigation by Hussain et al. (2018), who found that internal assessments and previous grades are the most frequently used factors in predicting students' academic performance. This is further supported by Saa et al. (2019a), where most of their analysed articles considered CGPA (cumulative grade point average) of all the past and present performances in a degree or program

The second-highest factor in predicting academic performance is demographics, which is represented in 37 of the studies in the sample. These factors contribute to a holistic understanding of the student population, considering the diverse backgrounds and contexts that may influence academic performance. This finding aligns with Alyahyan and Düşteğör's (2020) findings and those of Saa et al. (2019a). Twenty-four of the selected studies indicated that socio-economic factors affect students' academic performance prediction. The socio-economic factor includes place of residence, family history, and family income level. This finding is supported by the bin Roslan and Chen (2022) study. Hence, they should be included as predictors of students' academic performance.

Prior knowledge was the least cited theme, appearing in only four studies. In EDM, prior knowledge is the awareness of a topic based on previous learning. Prior knowledge was used to analyse student competence, enrolment choices, and performance prediction. The principal metric of prior knowledge relates to previous experience or specialization and is acquired through surveys. According to Saa et al. (2019a), factors reported in only a few studies are likely to have little or no influence on predictions of students' academic performance. Therefore, EDM researchers may have to re-evaluate the inclusion of these aspects in such a prediction or at least re-evaluate the predictors with which they are included so that they are matched with the best predictors to increase the accuracy in the algorithms of students' academic performance prediction.

RQ2: What are the key student involvement factors used in EDM to predict sub-Saharan African undergraduate STEM students' academic performance?

Generally, students' demographics, previous educational records, and socio-economic factors are categorized as static data, while learning behaviors, student engagement, and other multimodal data are referred to as dynamic (bin Roslan & Chen, 2022). In recent years, there has been an increasing amassing of multimodal data from

learning management systems, such as the frequency of uploading assignments, solving online quizzes, and accessing online material for modelling.

Among the 41 selected articles, only six studies used e-learning behaviours with previous educational records, students' demographics, and socio-economic factors. Most of the studies used static data to predict students' academic performance. However, using static data for students' academic performance prediction has some shortcomings. One significant limitation is the inability of static data to capture the dynamic and evolving nature of students' efforts in the learning process. Static variables, including demographics, previous academic records, and socio-economic factors, offer a fixed snapshot that fails to adapt to changes in student academic performance over time. This raises concerns about the predictive model's capacity to account for improvement or deterioration in performance that may occur during a program. Some studies also used students' e-learning behavioural data, obtained from LMSs, to track students' interactions and engagement within online learning environments. This student behavioural data includes student engagement data such as the frequency of uploading assignments, accessing online material, and solving online quizzes. These factors were crucial determinants of students' academic performance, corroborating the findings of Hussain et al. (2018).

Furthermore, static data may oversimplify the complex interplay of factors influencing academic outcomes. Predictive models may overlook subtle shifts in student engagement, learning habits, and response to interventions by focusing on unchanging variables. This oversimplification could compromise the model's ability to provide accurate predictions. While most studies relied on static data, including e-learning behaviours introduces a dynamic aspect to the predictive modeling process. Dynamic data, comprising learning behaviours, student engagement, and multimodal data, provides a more real-time perspective on students' academic journeys. This shift from static to dynamic data acknowledges the evolving nature of students' efforts and engagement throughout their educational experiences. The selected studies in this analysis with learning behaviours as input factors found that student engagement levels or participation frequencies positively influenced students' academic performance. This finding supports the work of other studies (Hussain et al. (2018)) in this area.

These findings, however, are challenging to generalize for several reasons. Firstly, studies used absolute frequencies as input factors. Since each course or program has its own set of unique demands, it is difficult to find generalizable thresholds for each learning behaviour in various programs. The unique nature of academic requirements in diverse educational settings makes pinpointing standardized benchmarks that hold true across the board challenging. Furthermore, the temporal aspect of data collection emerges as a crucial factor influencing the applicability of learning behaviours in predicting academic performance. The effectiveness of predicting outcomes appears to be dependent on the duration and timing of data collection. Except for the two studies ([34] and [35]) that collected learning behaviours over several weeks to identify low-performing students early, most studies that used learning behaviours for students' academic performance prediction at the end of a course were more likely to identify significant predictors than to predict anything.

7. Conclusion

This SLR identified the most frequently used factors influencing students' academic performance.

The exploration of EDM for predicting academic performance among sub-Saharan African undergraduate STEM students reveals a dynamic interplay of key student involvement factors. These factors are a mix of traditional and evolving variables, with the conventional inputs consisting of previous educational records, demographics, and socio-economic factors. Recent advances in data collection witness the inclusion of e-learning behaviours, such as assignment uploads, online quiz participation, and course material access. Integrating dynamic data, especially e-learning behaviours, provides a more comprehensive view of student engagement. However, challenges in generalisability arise due to varying behaviours across courses, and the absence of standardised thresholds complicates universal predictive measures. Temporal considerations highlight the need for a balanced approach between early identification and end-of-course predictions. Traditional factors offer a foundational understanding, while the inclusion of dynamic data signals a progressive shift. The challenges underline the roadmap for future research, urging ongoing exploration and enhancement of these factors to enhance the effectiveness of EDM in predicting academic performance. EDM's critical role in supporting Sub-Saharan African HEIs suggests directions for refining predictive models to enhance their effectiveness.

8. Limitations and Future Directions

The principal limitation of this study is that it concentrated on only STEM fields in HEIs. Furthermore, while the papers in the literature search were thoroughly screened using the abstracts and conclusions, this may have resulted in rejected studies with good content due to poor abstracts and conclusions. Notwithstanding these limitations, the study findings are broad enough to be valuable and applicable to scholars from other research fields beyond STEM.

Future research could attempt to replicate the methods with different disciplines or fields and explain the correlation between significant predicted factors and observed factors.

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Data Availability All data supporting the findings of this study are available within the paper.

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Appendix A

Table A.1: Selected Studies for Review

ID	Author and Year	Title	Country	Publication Type	Data Collection Source(s)
[S1]	Abed et al. (2019)	A Programme Recommendation Engine to Improve Student Placement at a South African Higher-Education Institution	South Africa	Thesis/Dissertation	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S2]	Adam et al. (2020)	Using Formative and Summative Assessments in Data Mining to Predict Students' Final Grades	Nigeria	International Research Journal of Innovations in Engineering and Technology (IRJET)	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S3]	A. I. Adekitan and O. Salau (2019)	The impact of engineering students' performance in the first three years on their graduation result using educational data mining	Nigeria	Heliyon	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S4]	Aderibigbe Israel Adekitan and Odunayo Salau (2019)	Toward an improved learning process: the relevance of ethnicity to data mining prediction of students' performance	Nigeria	SN Applied Sciences	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S5]	Afeni et al. (2019)	Students' Performance Prediction Using Classification Algorithms	Nigeria	International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications (IJACSA)	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S6]	Akinola and Abraham (2017)	A Comparative Analysis of Classification Techniques in Educational Data Mining Using Computer Programming Proficiency Indicators	Nigeria	Nigerian Journal of Science	Structured Questionnaire/Survey Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S7]	Bawah and Ussiph (2018)	Appraisal of the Classification Technique in Data Mining of Student Performance using J48 Decision Tree, k-Nearest Neighbor and Multilayer Perceptron Algorithms	Ghana	International Journal of Computer Applications	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S8]	Bokgoshi et al. (2021)	Predicting Students That Are At Risk Of Not Graduating In Record Time	South Africa	Thesis/Dissertation	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S9]	Buraimoh et al. (2021)	Predicting Student Success Using Student Engagement in the Online Component of a Blended-Learning Course	South Africa	Thesis/Dissertation	Students' Information Systems (SIS) Student online learning logs
[S10]	Dlamini et al. (2020)	Mining Campus Transfer Request Data	South Africa	International Conference on Soft Computing & Machine Intelligence (ISCMCI)	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S11]	Ekubo (2020)	Predictive system for characterizing low performance of Undergraduate students using machine learning techniques	South Africa	Thesis/Dissertation	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S12]	Ekubo and Esiefarienrhe (2019)	Attributes of low performing students in e-learning system using clustering technique	South Africa	International Conference on Computational Science and Computational Intelligence (CSCI)	Moodle LMS Logs

[S13]	Fagbola et al. (2019)	Development of Mobile-Interfaced Machine Learning-Based Predictive Models for Improving Students' Performance in Programming Courses	Nigeria	International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications (IJACSA)	Survey
[S14]	Gajadhur (2021)	Prototype Learning Analytics Dashboard (LAD) for an Introductory Statistics Course at UCT	South Africa	Thesis/Dissertation	Students' Information Systems (SIS) Student online learning logs
[S15]	Gatsheni and Katambwa (2018)	The Design of Predictive Model for the Academic Performance of Students at University Based on Machine Learning	South Africa	Journal of Electrical Engineering	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S16]	Girma (2019)	Developing a Predictive Model to Determine Higher Education Students' Academic Status Using Data Mining Technology	Ethiopia	Thesis/Dissertation	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S17]	Inyang et al. (2019)	Visual Association Analytics Approach to Predictive Modelling of Students' Academic Performance	Nigeria	International Journal of Modern Education and Computer Science	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S18]	Iyanda et al. (2018)	Predicting Student Academic Performance in Computer Science Courses: A Comparison of Neural Network Models	Nigeria	International Journal of Modern Education & Computer Science	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S19]	Jembere et al. (2017)	Matrix Factorisation for Predicting Student Performance	South Africa	World Engineering Education Forum (WEEF)	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S20]	Kasisi (2019)	An artificial neural network decision support model for university students progression	Kenya	Thesis/Dissertation	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S21]	Langa (2018)	Modelling student success or failure in electrical engineering at the vaal university of technology using machine learning techniques	South Africa	Thesis/Dissertation	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S22]	Lottering et al. (2020)	A Machine Learning Approach to Identifying Students at Risk of Dropout: A Case Study	South Africa	International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications (IJACSA)	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S23]	Makombe and Lall (2020)	A Predictive Model for the Determination of Academic Performance in Private Higher Education Institutions	South Africa	International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications (IJACSA)	Survey
[S24]	Matafeni (2017)	Predicting the Completion of a Student's Science Degree based only on their First-year Marks	South Africa	Thesis/Dissertation	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S25]	Mngadi (2020)	A Theoretical Model to Predict Undergraduate Learner Attrition using Background, Individual, and Schooling Attributes	South Africa	Thesis/Dissertation	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S26]	Mushi and Ngondya (2021)	Prediction of mathematics performance using educational data mining techniques	Tanzania	International Journal of Advanced Computer Research	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S27]	Mutau and Machoka (2019)	Enhancing Computer Students' Academic Performance through Predictive Modelling – A Proactive Approach	Kenya	International Conference on Computer Science & Education (ICCSE)	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S28]	Naidoo (2019)	Using Background, Individual and Pre-College Attributes for Student Placement in the Earth Sciences	South Africa	Thesis/Dissertation	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S29]	Ndou et al. (2020a)	A Case Study to Enhance Student Support Initiatives Through Forecasting Student Success in Higher-Education	South Africa	Advances in Science, Technology and Engineering Systems Journal	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S30]	Okike and Mogorosi (2020)	Educational Data Mining for Monitoring and Improving Academic Performance at University Levels	South Africa	International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications (IJACSA)	Moodle LMS Logs
[S31]	Ramaano et al. (2021)	Different Models Relating Prior Computer Experience with Performance in First Year Computer Science	South Africa	Thesis/Dissertation	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S32]	Ramokolo (2021)	Application of discrete-time survival analysis techniques in modelling student dropout: A case of engineering students at Tshwane University of Technology, South Africa	South Africa	Thesis/Dissertation	Students' Information Systems (SIS)

[S33]	Saheed et al. (2018)	Student performance prediction based on data mining classification techniques	Nigeria	Nigerian Journal of Technology	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S34]	Seota et al. (2021)	Modeling E-Behaviour, Personality and Academic Performance with Machine Learning	South Africa	Applied Sciences	Moodle LMS Logs
[S35]	Soobramoney (2021)	Early prediction of students at risk in a virtual learning environment using ensemble machine learning techniques	South Africa	Thesis/Dissertation	Students' Information Systems (SIS) Student online learning logs
[S36]	Taodzera (2018)	Predicting Student Performance Using Machine Learning Analytics	South Africa	Thesis/Dissertation	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S37]	Tegegne and Alemu (2018)	Educational Data Mining for Students' Academic Performance Analysis in Selected Ethiopian Universities	Ethiopia	Journal of Information and Knowledge Management	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S38]	Van Appel and Durandt (2019)	Investigating possibilities of predictive mathematical models to identify at-risk students in the south african higher education context	South Africa	Perspectives in Education	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S39]	Waidor and Akpojaro (2019)	The Use of Classification Algorithm for Forecasting the Academic Performance of Students of Biological Sciences, University of Africa, Toru-Orua	Nigeria	African Scientist	Students' Information Systems (SIS)
[S40]	Wanjau and Muketha (2018)	Improving Student Enrollment Prediction Using Ensemble Classifiers	Kenya	International Journal of Computer Applications Technology and Research	Student Questionnaire/Survey
[S41]	Yakubu and Abubakar (2021)	Applying machine learning approach to predict students' performance in higher educational institutions	Nigeria	International Journal of Systems & Cybernetics	Students' Information Systems (SIS)

Table A.2: Quality Assessment of Selected Studies

ID		Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Quality score
[S1]		1	1	0,5	1	0,5	1	5
[S2]		1	1	0,5	1	1	1	5,5
[S3]		1	1	0,5	1	1	1	5,5
[S4]		1	1	0,5	1	1	1	5,5
[S5]		1	1	1	0,5	1	1	5,5
[S6]		1	1	0,5	1	1	1	5,5
[S7]		1	1	0,5	1	1	1	5,5
[S8]		1	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	3,5
[S9]		1	1	0,5	1	1	1	5,5
[S10]		0,5	0,5	0,5	1	1	1	4,5
[S11]		1	1	0,5	1	1	1	5,5
[S12]		1	1	0,5	0,5	1	0,5	4,5
[S13]		1	1	0,5	1	1	0,5	5
[S14]		1	1	0,5	1	1	0,5	5
[S15]		1	1	0,5	1	0,5	0,5	4,5
[S16]		1	1	0,5	1	1	1	5,5
[S17]		1	1	1	0,5	1	0,5	5
[S18]		1	1	1	0,5	0	0	3,5
[S19]		1	1	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	4
[S20]		1	1	0,5	1	1	0,5	5
[S21]		1	1	0,5	1	1	1	5,5
[S22]		1		0,5	0,5	1	1	4
[S23]		1	0,5	0	0,5	1	1	4
[S24]		1	1	0,5	1	0,5	1	5
[S25]		1	1	0,5	1	1	1	5,5
[S26]		1	1	0,5	1	1	1	5,5
[S27]		1	1	0,5	1	1	1	5,5
[S28]		1	1	0,5	1	1	1	5,5
[S29]		1	1	0,5	1	1	1	5,5
[S30]		1	1	1	1	1	1	6
[S31]		1	0,5	0,5	1	1	1	5
[S32]		1	1	0,5	1	0,5	1	5
[S33]		1	1	1	1	1	1	6
[S34]		1	1	0,5	1	1	1	5,5
[S35]		1	1	1	1	1	1	6
[S36]		1	1	1	1	1	1	6
[S37]		1	1	0,5	1	0,5	0	4
[S38]		1	1	0,5	1	1	1	5,5
[S39]		1	1	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	4
[S40]		1	1	0,5	1	1	1	5,5
[S41]		1	1	0,5	1	1	1	5,5